

Emerging Role of IT in the Development of World Economy

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ABSTRACT

IT investment played a crucial role in the growth of the U.S. economy. IT prices is the key to understanding the resurgence of American economic growth. The period 1995 - 2003 have been sub-divided in order to focus on the response of IT investment to the accelerated decline in IT prices. With the growth of input per capita between

investments in tangible assets and investments in human capital, the world economy experienced a surge in investment in IT after 1995. With the help of different levels of output per capita, the differences in per capita output levels are primarily explained by differences in per capita input, rather than variations in productivity.

KEY WORDS: G7, GDP, Non-G7, Penn World Table, Soaring Level

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the impact of investment in information technology (IT) equipment and software on the recent resurgence in world economic growth. IT investment played a crucial role in the growth of the U.S. economy. The remarkable behavior of IT prices is the key to understanding the resurgence of American economic growth. The growth of IT investment jumped to double-digit levels after 1995 in all the G7 economies - *Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, United Kingdom and United States*. These economies account for nearly half of world output and a much larger share of world IT investment.

The surge of IT investment after 1995 resulted from a sharp acceleration in the rate of decline of prices of IT equipment and software. There was a drastic shortening of the product cycle for semiconductors from three (03) years to two (02) years, beginning in 1995. The world economy is divided among the G7 and Non-G7 industrialized economies, *Developing Asia, Latin America, Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union, North Africa and the Middle East, and Sub-Saharan Africa*. The fourteen major economies include the G7 economies and the developing and transition economies of *Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Mexico, Russia, and South Korea*.

Table 1. The World Economy : Shares in Size and Growth by Group, Region and Major Economies

Group / Region	Period 1989 - 1995			Period 1995 - 2003		
	GDP Growth	Average Share		GDP Growth	Average Share	
		GDP	Growth		GDP	Growth
World (110 Economies)	2.50	100.00	100.00	3.45	100.00	100.00
G7 (7 Economies)	2.18	47.44	41.33	2.56	45.26	33.62
Developing Asia (16)	7.35	20.76	61.13	5.62	26.05	42.56
Non - G7 (15)	2.03	8.38	6.77	3.01	8.13	7.10
Latin America (19)	3.06	8.35	10.20	2.11	8.07	4.94
Eastern Europe (14)	-7.05	9.32	-26.76	2.87	6.57	5.47
Sub - Sahara Africa (28)	1.21	2.13	1.03	2.88	2.01	1.68
North Africa and Middle East (11)	4.36	3.61	6.29	4.08	3.91	4.64

Group / Region	Period 1989 - 1995					Period 1995 - 2003				
	GDP Growth	Average GDP Share		Growth Share		GDP Growth	Average GDP Share		Growth Share	
		Group	World	Group	World		Group	World	Group	World
<i>Seven World Major Economies (G7)</i>										
Canada	1.39	4.90	2.32	3.12	1.29	2.51	4.78	2.17	4.69	1.58
France	1.30	7.10	3.37	4.23	1.75	1.92	6.76	3.06	5.05	1.70
Germany	2.34	10.80	5.12	11.58	4.79	0.86	10.20	4.63	3.41	1.15
Italy	1.52	7.42	3.52	5.17	2.14	1.48	6.99	3.17	4.05	1.36
Japan	2.56	16.23	7.70	19.03	7.88	1.39	15.73	7.13	8.54	2.88
United Kingdom	1.62	7.45	3.54	5.53	2.29	2.55	7.37	3.34	7.32	2.46
United States	2.43	46.11	21.87	51.34	21.26	3.56	48.16	21.76	66.92	22.46
All G7	2.18	100.00	47.40	100.00	41.40	2.56	100.00	45.30	100.00	33.60
<i>Seven Major Developing and Transition Economies (GD7)</i>										
Brazil	1.97	12.10	3.16	6.89	2.48	1.94	10.16	2.93	3.80	1.65
China	9.94	29.26	7.64	84.23	30.36	7.13	37.79	10.91	51.99	22.55
India	5.03	18.98	4.95	27.65	9.97	6.15	20.69	5.97	24.54	10.65
Indonesia	6.82	7.12	1.86	14.07	5.07	2.41	6.98	2.02	3.25	1.41
Mexico	2.19	7.48	1.95	4.74	1.71	3.56	6.74	1.95	4.63	2.01
Russian Federation	-8.44	19.92	5.20	-48.71	-17.56	3.18	12.17	3.52	7.46	3.24
South Korea	7.48	5.14	1.34	11.13	4.01	4.09	5.47	1.58	4.32	1.87
All GD7	3.45	100.00	26.10	100.00	36.00	5.18	100.00	28.90	100.00	43.40

The period 1995 - 2003 have been sub-divided in order to focus on the response of IT investment to the accelerated decline in IT prices. The world economic growth has undergone a powerful revival since 1995. The per capita growth rate jumped nearly a full percentage point from 2.50 % during 1989-1995 to 3.45 % in 1995-2003. The per capita growth of 3.45 % doubles world output per capita in a little over two decades, while slower growth of 2.50 % doubles per capita output in slightly less than three decades.

In the growth of world output (input growth and productivity), input growth greatly predominated. Productivity growth contributed only one-fifth of the total during 1989-1995, while input growth accounted for almost four-fifths. Similarly, input growth contributed more than 70 % of growth after 1995, while productivity accounted for less than 30 %.

With the growth of input per capita between investments in tangible assets (especially IT equipment and software) and investments in human capital, the world economy (all seven regions, and the fourteen major economies, except Indonesia and Mexico) experienced a surge in investment in IT after 1995. The soaring level of U.S. IT investment after 1995 was paralleled by jumps in IT investment throughout the industrialized world. The contributions of IT investment in Developing Asia, Latin America, Eastern Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, and Sub-Saharan Africa more than doubled after 1995, beginning from much lower levels. By far the most dramatic increase took place in Developing Asia.

With the help of different levels of output per capita (input per capita and productivity for the world economy, the seven economic regions, and the fourteen major economies), the differences in per capita output levels are primarily explained by differences in per capita input, rather than variations in productivity. Assuming U.S. output per capita in 2000 as 100.0, world output per capita was a relatively modest 23.9 in 2003 and assuming similar scales for input and productivity, world input per capita in 2003 was a substantial 42.4 and world productivity a robust 56.3.

WORLD ECONOMIC GROWTH, 1989-2003

In order to set the stage for analyzing the impact of IT investment on the growth of the world economy, first

consider the shares of world product and growth for each of the seven regions and the fourteen major economies presented in Table 1, GDP as a measure of output has been chosen. The Penn World Table is the primary data source on GDP and purchasing power parities for economies outside the G7 and the European Union.

The G7 economies accounted for slightly under half of world product from 1989-2003. The per capita growth rates of these economies - 2.18 % before 1995 and 2.56 % afterward - were considerably below world growth rates. The growth acceleration of 0.60 % for the G7 economies lagged behind the jump in world economic growth. The G7 shares in world growth were 41.3 % during 1989-1995 and 33.6 % in 1995-2003, well below the G7 shares in world product of 47.4 % and 45.3 %, respectively. During 1995-2003 the U.S. accounted for 21.8 % of world product and 48.2 % of G7 output. After 1995, Japan fell from its ranking as the world's second largest economy to third largest after China. Germany dropped from fourth place before 1995, following the U.S., China, and Japan, to fifth place during 1995-2003, ranking behind India as well. Japan remained the second largest of the G7 economies, while Germany retained its position as the leading European economy. France, Italy and the U.K. were similar in size, but less than half the size of Japan. Canada was the smallest of the G7 economies.

The U.S. growth rate jumped from 2.43 % during 1989-1995 to 3.56 % in 1995-2003. The period 1995-2003 included the shallow U.S. recession of 2001 and the ensuing recovery, as well as the IT-generated investment boom of the last half of the 1990's. The U.S. accounted for more than half of G7 growth before 1995 and more than two-thirds afterward. The U.S. share in world growth fell below its share in world product before 1995, but rose above the U.S. product share after 1995. By contrast Japan's share in world economic growth before 1995 exceeded its share in world product, but fell short of the product share after 1995. The remaining G7 economies had lower shares of world growth than world product before and after 1995.

The 16 economies of Developing Asia generated slightly more than a fifth of world output before 1995 and more than a quarter afterward. The rapidly increasing economies of China and India accounted for more than 60 % of Asian output in both periods.

The economies of Developing Asia grew at 7.35 % before 1995 and 5.62 % afterward. These economies were responsible for an astounding 61 % of world growth during 1989-1995.

Slightly less than half of this took place in China, while a little less than a third occurred in India. Developing Asia's share in world growth declined to 43 % during 1995-2003, remaining well above the region's share of 26.1 % of world product. China accounted for more than half of this growth and India about a quarter. The 15 Non-G7 industrialized economies generated more than eight % of world output during 1989-2003. These economies were responsible for lower shares in world growth than world product before and after 1995.

Prior to the fall of the Berlin Wall and the collapse of the Soviet Union, the 14 economies of Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union were larger in size than the Non-G7, generating 9.3 % of world product. All of the economies of Eastern Europe experienced a decline in output during 1989-1995. Collectively, these economies subtracted 26.8 % from world growth during 1989-1995, dragging their share of world product down to 6.6 %. During 1989-1995 Russia's economy was comparable in size to Germany's, but from 1995 to 2003 the Russian economy was only slightly larger than the U.K. economy.

During 1989-1995 the 10 % share of the Latin American economies in world growth exceeded their eight-and-a-half % share in world product. After 1995 these economies had a substantially smaller 6 % share in world growth, while retaining close to an eight-and-a-half share in world product with Brazil and Mexico responsible for more than 60 % of this. Brazil's share in world growth was below its 3 % share in world product before and after 1995, while Mexico's growth was lower than its product share before 1995 and higher afterward.

The eleven (11) economies of North Africa and the Middle East, taken together, were comparable in size to France, Italy, or the U.K., while the 30 economies of Sub-Saharan Africa, as a group, ranked with Canada. The economies of North Africa and the Middle East had a share in world growth of 6.3 % during 1989-1995, well above their 3.6 % share in world product. After 1995 their share in world growth fell to 4.6 %, still above the share in world product of 3.9 %. Growth in the economies of Sub-Saharan

Africa lagged behind their shares in world product during both periods.

SOURCES OF WORLD ECONOMIC GROWTH

In world economic growth during 1989-2003 between the contributions of capital and labour inputs and the growth of productivity, productivity frequently touted as the primary engine of economic growth, accounted for only 20-30 % of world growth. Nearly half of this growth can be attributed to the accumulation and deployment of capital and another a quarter to a third to the more effective use of labour. The second objective is to explore the determinants of the growth of capital and labour inputs, emphasizing the role of investment in information technology equipment and software and the importance of investment in human capital.

The estimates of capital input and property income from national accounting data for the G7 economies have been derived and the estimates of hours worked and labour compensation from labour force surveys for each of these economies have also been constructed. The contribution of labour inputs, classified by age, gender, educational attainment, and employment status, by weighting the growth rate of each type of labour input by its share in the value of output also measured. Finally, purchasing power parities for capital and labour inputs have been employed.

The investments in information technology equipment and software from investments in other assets for all 110 economies have been distinguished in our study. The estimates of IT investment from national accounting data for the G7 economies and those of the European Union before enlargement have been derived. The contribution of IT investment to economic growth by weighting the growth rate of IT capital inputs by the shares of these inputs in the value of output is measured. Similarly, the contribution of Non-IT investment is a share-weighted growth rate of Non-IT capital inputs. The contribution of capital input is the sum of these two components.

The U.S. data on investment in information technology and equipment is revised and updated. Data on IT investment for Canada have been taken from Statistics Canada. Data for the countries of the European Union have been developed for the European Commission is also taken. Finally, data for

Japan have been assembled. The WITSA Digital Planet Report (2002, 2004) is taken as the starting point for estimates of IT investment for the remaining economies. The labour input growth between the growth of hours worked and labour quality have been divided, where quality is defined as the ratio of labour input to hours worked. The contribution of labour input is the rate of growth of this input, weighted by the share of labour in the value of output. Finally, productivity growth is the difference between the rate of growth of output and the contributions of capital and labour inputs.

The contribution of capital input to world economic growth before 1995 was 1.18 %, a little more than 47 % of the growth rate of 2.50 %. Labour input contributed 0.79 % or slightly less than 32 %, while productivity growth of 0.53 % or just over 21 %. After 1995 the contribution of capital input climbed to 1.56 %, around 45 % of output growth, while the contribution of labour input rose to 0.89 %, around 26 %. Productivity increased to 0.99 % or nearly 29 % of growth. The contributions of capital and labour inputs greatly predominated over productivity as sources of world economic growth before and after 1995.

The contribution of capital input to world economic growth between IT equipment and software and Non-IT capital input have been divided. The contribution of IT almost doubled after 1995, less than a quarter to more than a third of the contribution of capital input. However, Non-IT was more important before and after 1995. The contribution of labour input between hours worked and labour quality have also been divided. Hours rose from 0.39 % before 1995 to 0.62 % after 1995, while labour quality declined from 0.40 % to 0.27 %. Labour quality and hours worked were almost equal in importance before 1995, but hours worked became the major source of labour input growth after 1995.

The acceleration in the world growth rate after 1995 was 0.95 %, almost a full percentage point. The contribution of capital input explained 0.38 % of this increase, while the productivity accounted for 0.46 %. Labour input contributed a relatively modest 0.10 %.

The jump in IT investment of 0.26 % was most important source of the increase in capital input. This can be traced to the stepped up rate of decline of IT prices after 1995. The substantial increase of 0.23 % in the contribution of hours worked was the most important component of labour input growth.

Table 2 presents the contribution of capital input to economic growth for the G7 economies, divided between IT and Non-IT. Capital input was the most important source of growth before and after 1995. The contribution of capital input before 1995 was 1.28 or almost three-fifths of the G7 growth rate of 2.18 %, while the contribution of 1.43 % after 1995 was 55 % of the higher growth rate of 2.56 %. Labour input growth contributed 0.49 % before 1995 and 0.46 % afterward, about 22 % and 18 % of growth, respectively. Productivity accounted for 0.42 % before 1995 and 0.67 % after 1995 or less than a fifth and slightly more than a quarter of G7 growth, respectively.

The powerful surge of IT investment in the U.S. after 1995 is mirrored in jumps in the growth rates of IT capital through the G7. The contribution of IT capital input for the G7 increased from 0.38 during the period 1989-1995 to 0.69 % during 1995-2003, rising from 30 % of the contribution of capital input to more than 48 %. The contribution of Non-IT capital input predominated in both periods, but receded slightly from 0.90 % before 1995 to 0.74 % afterward. This reflected more rapid substitution of IT capital input for Non-IT capital input in response to swiftly declining prices of IT equipment and software after 1995. The modest acceleration of 0.38 % in G7 output growth after 1995 was powered by investment in IT equipment and software, accounting for 0.31%, while the contribution of Non-IT investment slipped by 0.16 %. Before 1995 the contribution of labour quality of 0.42% accounted for more than 80 % of the contribution of G7 labour input, while the contribution of hours worked of 0.28 % explained more than 60% after 1995. The rising contribution of hours worked was offset by the declining contribution of labour quality, while productivity growth rose by 0.25%.

Table 2. Sources of Output Growth : 1995-2003 vs 1989-1995

Economy	Period 1989 - 1995						Period 1995 - 2003					
	GDP Gro wth	Source of Growth (% points per annum)					GDP Gro wth	Source of Growth (% points per annum)				
		Capital		Labour		TFP		Capital		Labour		TFP
		ICT	Non- ICT	Hrs	Qua- lity			ICT	Non- ICT	Hrs	Qua- lity	
World (110 Economies)	2.50	0.27	0.91	0.39	0.40	0.53	3.45	0.53	1.03	0.62	0.27	0.99
G7 (7 Economies)	2.18	0.38	0.90	0.07	0.42	0.42	2.56	0.69	0.74	0.28	0.18	0.67
Developing Asia (16)	7.35	0.15	1.73	1.19	0.42	3.86	5.62	0.43	2.27	0.81	0.38	1.72
Non - G7 (15)	2.03	0.32	0.68	0.21	0.21	0.61	3.01	0.49	0.77	1.06	0.20	0.49
Latin America (19)	3.06	0.16	0.58	1.20	0.37	0.75	2.11	0.39	0.61	1.10	0.39	3.06
Eastern Europe (14)	-7.05	0.10	-1.05	-0.86	0.36	-6.50	2.87	0.23	-0.81	0.01	0.39	3.06
Sub-Sahara Africa (28)	1.21	0.13	0.24	1.66	0.56	-1.39	2.88	0.29	0.68	1.18	0.42	0.32
N. Africa & M. East (11)	4.36	0.15	0.72	1.43	0.56	1.50	4.08	0.40	0.88	2.02	0.49	0.30
Seven World Major Economies (G7)												
Canada	1.39	0.49	0.27	0.07	0.55	0.01	2.51	0.65	0.61	0.68	0.16	0.42
France	1.30	0.19	0.93	-0.17	0.61	-0.26	1.92	0.36	0.75	0.22	0.07	0.52
Germany	2.34	0.26	1.05	-0.42	0.33	1.12	0.86	0.40	0.50	-0.24	0.09	0.11
Italy	1.52	0.26	0.86	-0.35	0.38	0.37	1.48	0.46	0.96	0.61	0.27	-0.82
Japan	2.56	0.31	1.16	-0.39	0.54	0.94	1.39	0.56	0.26	-0.32	0.22	0.67
United Kingdom	1.62	0.27	1.69	-0.73	0.49	-0.10	2.55	0.65	0.19	0.38	0.26	1.07
United States	2.43	0.49	0.71	0.57	0.36	0.31	3.56	0.88	1.01	0.50	0.17	0.99
All G7	2.18	0.38	0.90	0.07	0.42	0.42	2.56	0.69	0.74	0.28	0.18	0.67
Seven Major Developing and Transition Economies (GD7)												
Brazil	1.97	0.09	0.29	0.99	0.39	0.20	1.94	0.46	0.24	0.67	0.37	0.21
China	9.94	0.17	2.12	0.87	0.45	6.33	7.13	0.63	3.17	0.45	0.39	2.49
India	5.03	0.09	1.18	1.27	0.43	2.06	6.15	0.26	1.77	1.22	0.41	2.49
Indonesia	6.82	0.10	1.62	1.64	0.43	3.04	2.41	0.09	1.47	0.91	0.41	-0.47
Mexico	2.19	0.24	0.95	1.48	0.38	-0.87	3.56	0.23	1.11	1.76	0.31	0.14
Russian Federation	-8.44	0.07	-0.07	-1.02	0.37	-7.79	3.18	0.10	-1.30	0.21	0.44	3.73
South Korea	7.48	0.29	2.31	1.45	0.31	3.13	4.09	0.46	1.67	0.86	0.26	0.85
All GD7	3.45	0.13	1.17	0.72	0.41	1.03	5.18	0.40	1.70	0.74	0.39	1.96

In Developing Asia the contribution of capital input increased from 1.88 % before 1995 to 2.70 % after 1995, while the contribution of labour input fell from 1.61 % to 1.19 %. These opposing trends had a slightly positive impact on growth. The significant slowdown in the Asian growth rate from 7.35 % to 5.62 % can be traced entirely to a sharp decline in productivity growth from 3.86 to 1.72 %. Productivity explained slightly over half of Asian growth before 1995, but only 30 % after 1995. The first half of the 1990's was a continuation of the Asian Miracle. This period was dominated by the spectacular rise of China and India and the continuing emergence of the Gang of Four - Hong Kong, Singapore, South Korea, and Taiwan. However, all the Asian economies had growth rates considerably in excess of the world average of 2.50 %. The second half of the 1990's was dominated by the Asian financial crisis attributing Asian growth to input growth rather than productivity.

Developing Asia experienced a potent surge in investment in IT equipment and software after 1995. The contribution of IT investment more than doubled from 0.15 % to 0.43 %, explaining less than 8 % of the contribution of capital input before 1995, but almost 16 % afterward. The rush in IT investment was particularly powerful in China, rising from 0.17 % before 1995 to 0.63 % afterward. India fell substantially behind China, but outperformed the region as a whole, increasing the contribution of IT investment from 0.09 to 0.26 %. Indonesia was the only major economy to experience a decline in the contribution of both IT and Non-IT investment after 1995. South Korea's IT investment increased from 0.29 before 1995 to 0.46 % afterward, while Non-IT investment dropped as a consequence of the Asian financial crisis. The contribution of Non-IT investment in Asia greatly predominated in both periods and also accounted for most of the increase in the contribution of capital input after 1995. The contributions of hours worked and labour quality declined after 1995 with hours worked dominating in both periods.

Economic growth in the 15 Non-G7 industrialized economies accelerated much more sharply than G7 growth after 1995. The contribution of labour input slightly predominated over capital input before and after 1995. The contribution of labour input was 0.81 % before 1995, accounting for about 40 % of Non-G7 growth, and 1.26 after 1995, explaining 39 % of growth. The corresponding contributions of capital

input were 0.75 % and 1.12 %, explaining 37 and 34 % of Non-G7 growth, respectively. Non-G7 productivity also rose from 0.47 before 1995 to 0.89 % afterward; however, productivity accounted for only 23 and 27 % of growth in these two periods.

The impact of investment in IT equipment and software in the Non-G7 economies doubled after 1995, rising from 0.22 % to 0.44 % or from 29 % of the contribution of Non-G7 capital input to 39 %. This provided a substantial impetus to the acceleration in Non-G7 growth of 1.25 %. Non-IT investment explained another 0.14 % of the growth acceleration. However, the increased contribution of hours worked of 0.49 % and improved productivity growth of 0.42 % predominated. The collapse of economic growth in Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union before 1995 can be attributed almost entirely to a steep decline in productivity during the transition from socialism. This was followed by a modest revival in both growth and productivity after 1995, bringing many of the transition economies close to levels of output per capita that prevailed in 1989. The contribution of capital input declined both before and after 1995, even as the contribution of IT investment jumped from 0.09 to 0.26 %. Hour worked also declined in both periods, but labour quality improved substantially. Latin America's growth decelerated slightly after 1995, falling from 2.95 to 2.52 %. The contribution of labour input was 1.92 % before 1995 and 1.89 % afterward, accounting for the lion's share of regional growth in both periods. The contribution of capital input rose after 1995 from 0.72 % to 0.99 %, but remained relatively weak. Mexico's IT investment declined slightly after 1995, while Non-IT investment increased. Nonetheless the contribution of IT investment in Latin America more than doubled, jumping from 0.15 % before 1995 to 0.34 % afterward or from 21 % of the contribution of capital input to 34 %. Productivity was essentially flat from 1989 to 2001, rising by 0.31 % before 1995 and falling by 0.36 % after 1995. Productivity in Sub-Saharan Africa collapsed during 1989-1995 but recovered slightly, running at -1.63 % before 1995 and 0.36 % afterward. The contribution of labour input predominated in both periods, but fell from 2.77 % to 1.89 %, while the contribution of capital input rose from 0.52 % to 0.99 %. Productivity in North Africa and the Middle East, like that in Latin America, was essentially stationary from 1989-2001, falling from a positive rate of 0.50 % before 1995 to a negative rate of -0.46 % afterward.

WORLD OUTPUT, INPUT, AND PRODUCTIVITY

Table 3 describe and characterize the levels of output, input, and productivity for the world economy for the analysis of the world growth resurgence.

Table 3. Levels of Output and Input Per Captia and Productivity (US = 100 in 2000)

Region / Country	Output Per Captia			Input Per Captia			Productivity		
	1989	1995	2003	1989	1995	2003	1989	1995	2003
World (110 Economies)	18.9	20.0	23.9	38.5	38.5	42.4	49.0	52.0	56.3
G7 (7 Economies)	66.9	72.8	85.5	75.8	77.4	86.4	91.9	94.1	99.0
Developing Asia (16)	6.0	8.5	12.1	19.1	21.5	26.2	31.7	39.7	46.1
Non - G7 (15)	51.5	56.0	68.0	61.9	64.9	75.9	83.2	86.4	89.5
Latin America (19)	18.6	20.0	21.0	27.1	28.2	30.5	68.4	71.0	68.7
Eastern Europe (14)	34.3	22.5	29.3	43.2	41.4	42.6	79.4	54.4	68.8
Sub-Sahara Africa (28)	5.3	4.8	5.0	15.7	15.7	16.7	33.5	30.6	30.0
N. Africa & M. East (11)	12.5	14.2	17.0	22.3	23.2	27.3	55.9	61.1	62.3
<i>Seven World Major Economies (G7)</i>									
Canada	79.4	80.2	91.0	75.0	75.7	83.2	105.9	105.9	109.5
France	54.5	57.4	64.7	53.7	57.4	62.1	101.5	100.0	104.2
Germany	59.0	65.5	69.4	71.6	74.3	98.0	82.4	88.2	89.0
Italy	57.7	62.5	69.9	55.9	59.2	70.7	103.2	105.6	98.9
Japan	56.3	64.4	70.8	72.5	78.3	81.7	77.7	82.2	86.7
United Kingdom	56.9	61.8	73.7	61.7	67.5	73.9	92.2	91.6	99.8
United States	80.6	86.3	106.4	84.8	89.1	101.4	95.5	96.9	104.9
All G7	66.9	72.8	85.5	72.8	77.4	86.4	91.9	94.1	99.0
<i>Seven Major Developing and Transition Economies (GD7)</i>									
Brazil	19.9	20.5	21.5	29.3	29.8	30.8	67.9	68.7	69.8
China	4.8	8.1	13.4	17.9	20.7	28.0	26.9	39.3	48.0
India	5.0	6.0	8.6	15.9	17.0	19.9	31.2	35.3	43.1
Indonesia	8.3	11.3	12.2	23.7	26.8	29.9	35.3	42.3	40.7
Mexico	22.2	22.3	26.6	28.0	29.7	34.9	79.3	75.3	76.1
Russian Federation	41.8	25.1	33.5	50.0	48.0	47.4	83.6	52.4	70.6
South Korea	24.3	35.8	46.5	37.1	45.4	55.0	65.4	78.9	84.5
All GD7	9.0	10.2	14.0	24.4	24.0	28.3	36.8	42.4	49.6

The G7 economies led the seven economic regions in output per capita, input per capita, and productivity throughout the period 1989-2003. Output per capita in the G7 was, nonetheless, well below U.S. levels. Taking U.S. output per capita in 2000 as 100.0, G7 output per capita was 66.9 in 1989, 72.8 in 1995 and 85.5 in 2003. For comparison: U.S. output per capita was 80.6, 86.3, and 106.4 in these years. The output gap between the U.S. and the other G7 economies widened considerably, especially since 1995. Canada was very close to the U.S. in output per capita in 1989, but dropped substantially behind by 1995. The U.S.-Canada gap widened further during the last half of the 1990's. Germany, Japan, Italy, and the U.K. had similar levels of output per capita throughout 1989-2003, but remained considerably behind North America. France lagged the rest of the G7 in output per capita in 1989 and failed to make up lost ground. The U.S. was the leader among the G7 economies in input per capita throughout the period 1989-2003. Taking the U.S. as 100.0 in 2000, G7 input per capita was 72.8 in 1989, 77.4 in 1995, and 86.4 in 2003, while U.S. input per capita was 84.4, 89.1, and 101.4, respectively. Canada, Germany, and Japan were closest to U.S. levels of input per capita with Canada ranking second in 1989 and 2003 and Japan ranking second in 1995. France lagged behind the rest of the G7 in input per capita throughout the period with Italy and the U.K. only modestly higher. Productivity in the G7 has remained close to U.S. levels, rising from 91.7 in 1989 to 93.9 in 1995 and 96.7 in 2001, with the U.S. equal to 100.0 in 2000. Canada was the productivity leader throughout 1989-2003 with Italy and France close behind. The U.S. occupied fourth place in 1989 and 1995, but rose to second in 2003. Japan made substantial gains in productivity, but lagged behind the other members of the G7 in productivity, while Germany surpassed only Japan. Differences among the G7 economies in output per capita can be largely explained by differences in input per capita rather than gaps in productivity. The range in output was from 64.7 for France to 106.4 for the U.S., while the range in input was from 62.1 for France to 101.4 for the U.S. Productivity varied more

narrowly from 86.7 for Japan to 109.5 for Canada with French productivity of 104.2 closely comparable to the U.S. In the economies of Developing Asia output per capita rose spectacularly from 6.0 in 1989 to 8.5 in 1995 and 12.1 in 2003 with the U.S. equal to 100.0 in 2000. Levels of output per capita in Asia's largest economies, China and India, remained at 13.4 and 8.6, respectively, in 2003. These vast shortfalls in output per capita relative to the industrialized economies are due mainly to differences in input per capita, rather than variations in productivity. Developing Asia's levels of input per capita were 19.1 in 1989, 21.5 in 1995, and 26.2 in 2003, while Asian productivity levels were 31.7, 39.7, and 46.1, respectively.

China made extraordinary gains in output per capita, growing from 4.8 in 1989 to 8.1 in 1995 and 13.4 in 2003 with the U.S. equal to 100.0 in 2000. India had essentially the same output per capita as China in 1989, but grew less impressively to levels of only 6.0 in 1995 and 8.6 in 2003. China's input per capita - 17.9 in 1989, 20.7 in 1995, and 28.0 in 2001 - exceeded India's throughout the period. India's 31.2 productivity level in 1989 considerably surpassed China's 26.9. China's productivity swelled to 39.3 in 1995, outstripping India's 35.3. China expanded its lead with a productivity level of 48.0 in 2003 by comparison with India's 43.1.

Indonesia and South Korea grew impressively from 1989 to 1995, but fell victim to the Asian financial crisis during the period 1995-2003.

Indonesia maintained its lead over India in output per capita, but dropped behind China in 2003. Indonesia led both China and India in input per capita during 1989-2003. Indonesia's productivity level led both China and India in 1995, but fell behind both economies by 2003. South Korea made substantial gains in productivity, achieving a level close to Japan in 2003, while falling considerably short of Japan's impressive input per capita. The 15 Non-G7 industrialized economies, taken together, had levels of output per capita comparable to Germany, Italy, Japan, and the U.K. during 1989-2003. Input per capita for the 15 Non-G7 economies was also very

close to these four G7 economies. However, productivity for the group was comparable to that of Germany, the second lowest in the G7.

Before the beginning of the transition from socialism in 1989, output per capita in Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union was 34.3, well above the world economy level of 18.9, with the U.S. equal to 100.0 in 2000. The economic collapse that accompanied the transition reduced output per capita to 22.5 by 1995, only modestly higher than the world economy level of 20.0. A mild recovery between 1995 and 2003 brought the region back to 29.3, below the level of 1989, but well above the world economy average of 23.9. Input in the region was stagnant at 43.2 in 1989, 41.4 in 1995, and 42.6 in 2003. Productivity collapsed along with output per capita, declining from 79.4 in 1989 to 54.4 in 1995, before climbing back to 68.8 in 2003.

The downturn in output per capita and productivity was especially severe in the economies of the former Soviet Union. Russia's level of output per capita fell from 41.8 in 1989 to 25.1 in 1995 before recovering feebly to 33.5 in 2003. Russian input per capita remained essentially unchanged throughout the period 1989-2003, while productivity mirrored the decline and subsequent recovery in output, falling from a West European level of 83.6 in 1989 to 52.4 in 1995 before recovering to 70.6 in 2003. We conclude that the transition from socialism failed to restore Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union to pre-transition levels of output and input per capita by 2003, while productivity remained weaker than before the transition.

For the Latin American region output per capita rose from 18.6 to 21.0 during 1989-2003, input per capita rose from 27.1 to 33.0, but productivity was essentially unchanged at about two-thirds of the U.S. level in 2000. The stall in productivity from 1989 to 2003 was pervasive, contrasting sharply with the rise in productivity in the G7 economies, the Non-G7 industrialized economies, and Developing Asia. Nonetheless, Latin America's lagging output per capita was due chiefly to insufficient input per capita, rather than a shortfall in productivity.

Brazil's economic performance has been anemic at best and has acted as a drag on the growth of Latin America and the world economy. Despite productivity levels comparable to the rest of Latin America, Brazil was unable to generate substantial growth in input per capita. Although Mexico lost ground in productivity between 1989 and 2003, rising input per capita produced gains in output per capita after 1995, despite a slight decline in the contribution of IT investment. Output and input per capita in Sub-Saharan Africa was the lowest in the world throughout the period 1989-2003, but the level of productivity was slightly higher than Developing Asia in 1989. All the economies of North Africa and the Middle East fell short of world average levels of output and input per capita. Output per capita grew slowly but steadily for the region as a whole during 1989-2003, powered by impressive gains in input per capita, but with stagnant productivity.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

1. World economic growth, led by the industrialized economies and Developing Asia, experienced a strong resurgence after 1995. Developing Asia accounted for an astonishing 60 % of world economic growth before 1995 and 40 % afterward, with China alone responsible for half of this, but output per capita remained well below the world average. Sub-Saharan Africa and North Africa and the Middle East languished far below the world average. Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union lost enormous ground during the transition from socialism and have yet to recover completely.
2. The growth trends most apparent in the U.S. have counterparts throughout the world. Investment in tangible assets, including IT equipment and software, was the most important source of growth. However, Non-IT investment predominated. The contribution of labour input was next in magnitude with labour quality dominant before 1995 and hours worked afterward. Finally, productivity was the least

important of the three sources of growth, except during the Asian Miracle before 1995.

3. The leading role of IT investment in the acceleration of growth in the G7 economies is especially pronounced in the U.S., where IT is coming to dominate the contribution of capital input. The contribution of labour input predominated in the Non-G7 industrialized economies, as well as Latin America, Eastern Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, and North Africa and the Middle East. Productivity growth was the important source of growth in Developing Asia before 1995, but assumed a subordinate role after 1995. Productivity has been stagnant or declining in Latin America, Eastern Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, and North Africa and the Middle East.
4. All seven regions of the world economy experienced a surge in investment in IT equipment and software after 1995. The impact of IT investment on economic growth has been most striking in the G7 economies. The rush in IT

investment was especially conspicuous in the U.S., but jumps in the contribution of IT capital input in Canada, Japan, and the U.K. were only slightly lower. France, Germany, and Italy also experienced a surge in IT investment, but lagged considerably behind the leaders. While IT investment followed similar patterns in the G7 economies, Non-IT investment varied considerably and explains important differences among growth rates.

5. Although the surge in investment in IT equipment and software is a global phenomenon, the variation in the contribution of this investment has increased considerably since 1995. Following the G7, the next most important increase was in Developing Asia, led by China. The Non-G7 industrialized economies followed Developing Asia. The role of IT investment more than doubled after 1995 in Latin America, Eastern Europe, and North Africa and the Middle East, and Sub-Saharan Africa.

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